

ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL DESIGN OF CARBON FOAM LIGAMENT AT NANO SCALE FOR OPTIMAL STIFFNESS AND MULTIFUNCTIONALITY

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SUMMARY: Microscopic observation of carbon foam reveals aligned graphitic ligament microstructure resulting in orthotropic ligament properties. It is known that the structural response of open cell foam is due to the combined bending, stretching (axial), and shear deformation of the ligament. In order to optimize the foam bulk response (stiffness) the effect of the respective deformation modes of the ligament needs to be known, which is not trivial. The material orthotropy of the ligament makes the phenomenon more complex for optimizing mechanical stiffness without sacrificing the thermal and electrical properties that graphitic microstructure offers. In this study, an analysis is performed to define a design of material microstructure of carbon foam ligament to optimize the stiffness of carbon foam as well as retaining its thermal and electrical properties. The analysis is based on a closed form expression developed correlating the ligament deformation modes with the foam bulk response. It is analyzed that the zigzag formation of graphine sheets in the ligament microstructure provides improvement in the foam bulk stiffness as well as retaining the inherent superior thermal and electrical conductivity of carbon foam.

KEY WORDS: Graphitic foam, ligament modulus, microstructure, orthotropic foam ligament, bending, shear, and foam ligament material design space.

INTRODUCTION

Unlike many other types of foam, microstructural observation reveals that carbon foam ligament possesses orthotropic material characteristics. The orthotropic material characteristics of carbon foam ligament are due to the aligned and folded graphine sheet formation in the microstructure of carbon foam, as shown in figure 1. At the ligament nodes, the carbon microstructure appears to be amorphous in nature with no preferred aligned orientation of graphitic planes. Whereas, along the ligament length alignment of the graphitic planes appears more prevalent giving rise to orthotropic material properties of carbon foam ligament. In order to develop carbon foam as a viable multifunctional material, its mechanical performance needs to be optimized. Thus, optimization of the ligament orthotropic microstructure is desirable to tailor the foam bulk response.

There is an abundance of literature on modeling foam properties, especially on foam containing ligament of isotropic properties. Among the modeling efforts, the most widely used reference is that of Gibson and Ashby [1] and Warren and Kraynik [2]. Zhu, et al. [3] and Christensen [4]

developed a few closed form relations for bulk properties of foam assuming membrane behavior of foam ligaments. But all these work is limited to foam ligaments possessing isotropic properties. Due to complex three-dimensional orientations of the ligaments, as well as ligaments of varying cross section possessing material orthotropy, the implementation of the orthotropic microstructural characteristics in an analytical model to predict the bulk response is not trivial. In this regard, Sihn and Roy [5] and Li, *et al.* [6] developed two carbon foam models addressed at two different scale levels (microscopic and macroscopic) to correlate salient foam ligament microstructural characteristics with the bulk response.

Figure 1. (a) A representative microstructure of carbon foam, (b) an enlarged view of folded and aligned graphine sheets (planes) formation in the foam ligament microstructure.

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The microscopic model, Sihn and Roy [5], focused on characteristic microstructural scale (micron scale) level, is to analyze the effect of material orthotropy to foam response, and the macroscopic model is to thoroughly analyze the effect of the ligament deformation behavior to the bulk response. The microscopic model [5] development capturing the details of foam formation through bubble nucleation from the vertices of a tetrahedron as well as ligament cross sectional shape variation and ligament material orthotropy is schematically shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Microstructural modeling of foam formation capturing salient feature of ligament shape and material orthotropy [5].

The macroscopic model, Li, *et al.* [6], contains tetrakaidecahedral ligament configuration containing 36 ligaments in the model RVE. Since the ligament microstructural details that were implemented in the tetrahedral (microscopic) model could not feasibly be implemented in the 36 ligament RVE, the ligament microstructural characteristics are homogenized and ligaments are represented as homogeneous beam elements in the macroscopic model, Figure 3.

Figure 3. Macroscopic model [6] representing the tetrakaidecahedral ligament configuration of foam to analyze bulk response.

Representing the ligaments as beam elements made the model analytically manageable and efficient. However, the macroscopic model provides simple closed form expressions for predicting foam bulk properties correlating that with the ligament microstructural characteristics. The closed form expression, Eq. (1), below represents the bulk effective modulus of foam correlating with the ligament material orthotropy and its three deformation modes (bending, stretching and shear), where E , G , ρ , and c are Young's modulus, shear modulus, density, and radius of gyration of the ligament, respectively. E_z^* is the foam bulk modulus and k_1 is the shape factor of the ligament.

$$E_z^* = \frac{Ec\rho^2}{0.07872 + \left[1.171875 + 1.218750k_1 \frac{E}{G} \right] c\rho} \quad (1)$$

↑ **Bending**
 ↑ **Stretching**
 ↑ **Shear**

The alignment of graphine sheets in the ligament microstructure of carbon foam, as demonstrated by several researchers that attributes to the ligament material orthotropy can be controlled to tailor its microstructural configuration. Thus, the powerful closed form expression of correlating the orthotropic ligament properties with foam bulk response, Eq. (1) above, provides a unique methodology of analyzing and tailoring the ligament microstructural configuration, hence a mechanism of material design of configuring the graphitic orientation of the ligament microstructure at the nano meter scale level to optimizing carbon foam bulk response.

Figure 4. The effect of bending, shear and stretching (axial) ligament moduli on the bulk response of carbon foam.

In Figure 4, the effect of the ligament bending, axial, and shear moduli on the bulk foam modulus is studied for varying foam density. As is shown in Figure 4, if the ligament microstructure were to design to possess infinite shear and axial moduli, the foam bulk modulus would increase dramatically with increasing density, as long as the bending moduli of the ligament remains strong. This conjecture is further demonstrated in Figure 5, where it is shown that in order to improve the bulk modulus, the orthotropy ratio (E/G) of the ligament should be kept low (near to the isotropic value).

Figure 5. Design space for optimizing bulk modulus of carbon foam for varying orthotropic ratio (E/G) of foam ligament.

In order for carbon foam to retain its superior thermal and electrical conductivity, we need highly aligned graphine sheets, Figure 6. For highly aligned graphitic ligament microstructure on the other hand, due to weak van der Waals force between the graphine sheets, high bending and shear moduli in the ligaments are not achievable. Thus, to improve bending and shear moduli, at the same time retaining the desirable thermal and electrical characteristics through aligned graphine sheets, a zigzag graphine sheet configuration is proposed; the schematic configuration is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Microstructure of highly aligned graphine sheets in graphitic carbon.

Figure 7. The schematic view of zigzag graphine sheet configuration in foam ligament.

The calculation of the bending stiffness of the zigzag configuration of the graphine sheets is given in Appendix A. The normalized bending stiffness of the zigzag configuration, obtained from Appendix A, is shown in Figures 8 and 9. Figures 8 and 9 revealed that, due to zigzag configuration of the graphine sheets, the ligament bending rigidity increases dramatically with the number of zigzag sheets. The shear rigidity is also expected to increase similarly due to locking mechanism of the zigzag configuration.

Figure 8. Bending rigidity of the zigzag configuration with increasing graphine sheets.

Figure 9. The data in Figure 8 plotted in log-log scale to illustrate the advantage of zigzag microstructure in foam ligament.

CONCLUSIONS

A methodology is presented to improve the bulk modulus of carbon foam by tailoring the microstructure of the foam ligament. Microscopic observation of carbon foam reveals aligned graphitic ligament microstructure resulting in orthotropic ligament properties. It is known that the structural response of open cell foam is due to the combined bending, stretching (axial), and shear deformation of the ligament. The material orthotropy of the ligament makes the phenomenon more complex for optimizing mechanical stiffness without sacrificing the thermal and electrical properties that aligned graphitic microstructure known to offer. In this study, an analysis is performed to define a design of material microstructure of carbon foam ligament to optimize the stiffness of carbon foam as well as retaining its thermal and electrical properties. The analysis is based on a closed form expression developed correlating the ligament deformation modes with the foam bulk response. It is shown in this parametric study that the zigzag formation of graphine sheets in the ligament microstructure provides improvement in the foam bulk stiffness as well as retaining the inherent superior thermal and electrical conductivity of carbon foam. Suitable processing scheme needs to develop to achieve such zigzag microstructure in carbon foam ligament to bring true multifunctionality in carbon foam.

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APPENDIX A

Calculation of bending rigidity of the zigzag graphine sheet configuration

Figure A1. Schematic cross section of foam ligament composed of a stack of flat graphine sheets

- h_g : graphine sheet thickness (~ 0.363 nm)
 h_f : spacing between adjacent graphine sheets (~ 0.363 nm)
 h : ligament thickness (total thickness of the sheet stack)
 b : width of the ligament
 n_g : Number of graphine sheets

Figure A2. Schematic zigzag configuration and its equivalence for calculating the bending rigidity.

The bending stiffness of the ligament of stack of flat graphine sheets, I_g

$$I_g = n_g \frac{bh_g^3}{12}$$

Normalized bending rigidity of the ligament of folded graphine sheets

$$\frac{I_f}{I_g} = \frac{n_f}{n_g} \left[1 + \frac{3h_f^2}{2h_g^2} + \frac{h_f^3}{bh_g^2} \right] + \frac{12}{h_g^2} \left(1 + \frac{h_f}{b} \right) (h_g + h_f)^2 \frac{2h_g}{(h_g + h_f)n_f} \sum_i^{n_f} i^2$$

Also, for convenience, the annotation used in Figures 8 and 9, we define $I_n = \frac{2h_g}{(h_g + h_f)n_f} \sum_i^{n_f} i^2$

In summary, I_n is the most contributing factor in enhancing the ligament bending rigidity due to the zigzag sheet configuration.